

GRID METHOD BASED STORE SEPARATION SUITE USING PARANAM MESH FREE SOLVER

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Abstract

A store separation suite based on Point Prediction methodology was developed at CSIR-National Aerospace Laboratories (NAL) using PARANAM (Parallel NAL MCIR) mesh free CFD solver along with 6-DOF code and dynamic point cloud pre-processor [7,8]. This store separation suite is well validated and tested and is being used widely for various strategic store separation projects at CSIR-NAL [7,8]. However, in some scenarios point prediction based method is difficult to employ owing to either large number of trajectory studies or time and resource requirements. In such scenarios a quick but sufficiently accurate method is needed. The Grid method which is an approximate method based on aerodynamic database has been used to develop a store separation suite to achieve the same. In this work we have exploited mesh free nature of PARANAM solver to generate the aerodynamic database required for Grid method efficiently. The suite has been applied to standard Eglin test case for carrying out validation. Further we have demonstrated the utility of such a tool in parametric studies for assessing sensitivity.

Keywords: *Grid Method, Point Prediction Method, Store Separation, 6-DOF, Mesh-free Solver*

Introduction

Store separation studies are required before any new store is released from an old aircraft or a new aircraft is introduced in service or an old aircraft undergoes substantial changes, in order to ensure safe release and minimum deviation of store from the intended store trajectory. Prior trajectory prediction is crucial as otherwise it can lead to loss of aircraft and pilot. Traditionally there are three approaches to carry out any store separation studies. They are wind tunnel testing, CFD simulations and flight tests. The modern approach is to use all the three methods synergistically to reduce the flight tests required and aid in faster and safer clearance of stores.

CFD based store separation simulations can be done in two ways. One way is CFD based Point Prediction method where aerodynamic forces and moments acting on the store at each time step are predicted using CFD [7] and the other is CFD based Grid method in which aerodynamic forces and moments acting on the store at each time step are calculated by interpolating them from an existing aerodynamic database. A store separation suite based on Point Prediction methodology was already developed at CSIR-NAL. It is well validated and tested with experimental and flight test data for several cases. A number of store separation simulations have been undertaken by CSIR-NAL using this tool for various national aerospace

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programs. Based on this experience, it was found that in some scenarios Grid method based suite can meet some demands of store clearance which are difficult to be met with Point Prediction based suite.

One such scenario is where large number of store separation simulations have to be carried out. Sensitivity analysis for various parameters like ejector force, altitude, moment of inertia, weight, c.g. location, etc., can increase the number of simulations to be carried out exponentially. This is because, if we consider three variations in each of the above five parameters the number of trajectories to be simulated are $243(3^5)$. Carrying out these number of simulations using Point Prediction method requires large amount of time and resource. In these situations, Grid method can save lot of time and effort. With Grid method any number of trajectories can be generated in seconds.

Other such scenario is during flight tests, where any need for on-site trajectory prediction cannot be simulated using Point Prediction method based suite, which requires huge computing resources. In contrast, Grid method based suite can predict trajectory using on-site computers in a matter of seconds.

Also, studies show that a combination of Point Prediction method and Grid method for predicting store trajectories is superior to either alone [9]. It is because Grid method requires a large aerodynamic database to be created. In the initial stage of any store separation project before any aerodynamic database is generated, Point Prediction method can be used to predict trajectory. This trajectory data can also be used to reduce the size of aerodynamic database to be generated. Once the aerodynamic database is created any trajectory can be predicted using Grid method in just few seconds.

With these merits in mind, a store separation suite based on Grid method is developed at CSIR-NAL. This paper discusses details of this Grid method and use of meshfree solver to efficiently generate the aerodynamic database. It also discusses testing and validation of this method using a standard store separation problem. The store trajectory simulated with Grid method based store separation suite is compared with store trajectory predicted with Point Prediction method based store separation suite. These simulated trajectories are also compared with experimental data wherever available. Also, merits of using Grid method based store separation suite is established by studying the effect of changes in some parameters on the characteristics of separation. Since

aerodynamic database is already available these type of studies can be quickly carried out using Grid method.

Store Separation Suite Using Grid Method

Grid method based store separation suite needs

- aerodynamic database,
- interpolation code and
- 6-DOF solver

A flow chart of how Grid method based store separation suite works is shown in Fig.1 and discussed as follows:

Aerodynamic database is used by interpolation code to predict aerodynamic forces and moments acting on store in its current position. These aerodynamic forces and moments are then used by 6-DOF solver along with inertial properties of store and ejector forces to predict position of store for next time step. At this new position of store, interpolation code again uses aerodynamic database to predict aerodynamic forces and moments acting on store. These new aerodynamic forces and moments are used by 6-DOF along with other inputs to predict subsequent position of store. This process is continued until the trajectory of store is computed.

Aerodynamic Database Using PARANAM Mesh Free Solver

Aerodynamic forces and moments acting on store have to be generated for all possible variations of the considered parameters. For any mesh based CFD solver, new mesh has to be generated for every possible variation in position and orientation of store. This is a tedious process which will take huge amount of time and makes the process of aerodynamic database generation laborious.

PARANAM mesh free solver which works on point clouds allows us to automate the entire process of point cloud generation for every possible variation in position and orientation of store by use of a dynamic cloud combiner. PARANAM is a highly scalable parallel mesh free Euler solver developed at CSIR-NAL which works on LSKUM-MCIR (Least squares kinetic upwind mesh free method-Modified CIR) scheme [1, 2, 3, 4]. Higher order accuracy is achieved in this scheme by using a compact stencil.

In the present study, the various parameters which are used to generate aerodynamic database are Mach number, z-position of store, pitch and yaw of store. The displacement of store in x, y-direction is much less when compared to movement in z-direction in the near field of aircraft. In this case, the variation in x, y-position of store need not be considered for aerodynamic database generation since the change in aerodynamic forces and moments due to change in these parameters will be minor.

4-Dimensional Linear Interpolation Code

A 4-dimensional linear interpolation code was developed corresponding to four parameters Mach number, position of store in z-direction, pitch and yaw of store. These four parameters were used to generate aerodynamic database. This interpolation code uses aerodynamic database to predict aerodynamic forces and moments acting on store at any given Mach number, position and orientation of store after its release.

Details of Store Separation Problem

The store separation problem considered here is AEDC Eglin test case which is a standard store separation problem for testing and validation of any store separation tool [5]. Geometry for AEDC Eglin test case is shown in Fig.2. For this test case, experimental data of store separation characteristics is available for Mach number of 1.2.

In this study, we have done store separation simulations using Grid method for Mach number of 1.2. For this study, the aerodynamic database was generated using CFD at two Mach numbers 1.15 and 1.25. Further, for these Mach numbers, five different positions of z below aircraft were considered and for each of these z-positions a sweep of pitch and yaw of store were used. Sensitivity analysis was also carried out for change in ejector forces acting on store. A variation of ten, twenty and thirty percent in ejector force was considered and a study was done to find effect of ejector force on simulated trajectory.

Results

The predicted store trajectory using Grid method based store separation suite is compared with experimental test results and store trajectory computed using Point Prediction method based store separation suite. The displacements and Euler angles with time for Mach number of 1.2 obtained using Grid method, Point Prediction method and

experiments is shown in Fig.3(a) and Fig.3(b) respectively. It can be clearly seen that both displacements and Euler angles obtained using grid method compare very well with point prediction method. Further the comparison with experiments is also satisfactory. Fig.4 shows displacement and Euler angles for variation of ejector forces. Grid method correctly captures the variation in z displacement and pitch due to ejector force variation. X-displacement, Y-displacement, roll and yaw are generally not affected hugely by ejector force variation. This has been correctly predicted by Grid method.

Conclusion

The Grid method Store Separation Suite based on meshfree method has been developed. The aerodynamic database has been generated efficiently using PARANAM mesh free solver. As explained earlier the mesh free nature does away the repeated grid generation required by any mesh based solver. This suite has been verified by comparing results with Point Prediction method and is also validated by comparing with experimental results. Further it has been demonstrated that the effect of variation of ejector force can be easily assessed using this method. Similarly effect of variation of other relevant parameters can be easily generated. Further the knowledge of statistical variations of the parameters involved can be used to generate a population of trajectories as the method is very time efficient. This will lead to efficient and effective sensitivity analysis. Use of Grid method based suite in conjunction with Point Prediction method based suite for any store separation project can lead to faster and safer store clearance.

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Fig.1

Fig.2 Aircraft with Store in Initial Position

(a)

(b)

Fig.3 Mach Number = 1.2 (a) Displacements (b) Angles

Fig.4 Ejector Force Variation (a) Displacements (b) Angles

PSLV-C45 Successfully Launches EMISAT and 28 Customer Satellites

India's Polar Satellite Launch Vehicle (PSLV-C45) successfully launched EMISAT and 28 International Customer Satellites from Satish Dhawan Space Centre (SDSC) SHAR, Sriharikota. This flight marked the first mission of PSLV-QL, a new variant of PSLV with four strap-on motors.

PSLV-C45 lifted off from the Second Launch Pad and injected India's EMISAT into a 748 km sun-synchronous polar orbit, 17 minutes and 12 seconds after lift-off. After separation, the two solar arrays of EMISAT were deployed automatically and the ISRO Telemetry Tracking and Command Network at Bengaluru assumed control of the Satellite.

EMISAT is a Satellite built around ISRO's Mini Satellite-2 bus weighting about 426 kg. The satellite is intended for electromagnetic spectrum measurement. The 28 International Customer Satellites, together weighing about 220 kg, are from four Countries, namely, Lithuania (2), Spain (1), Switzerland (1) and USA (24). These foreign satellites were launched as part of commercial arrangements.

The payloads carried by PS4 are Automatic Identification System from ISRO, Automatic Packet Repeating System from AMSAT, India and Advanced Retarding Potential Analyzer for ionospheric studies from Indian Institute of Space Science and Technology.

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